

THE ROLE OF STAGES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF NON- PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14987361>

Abstract. This article discusses the development of a model for the development of creative competence in non-philological students in the process of teaching English. Through this model, the results and stages of developing creative competence in teaching English in the educational process are discussed.

Keywords: English language teaching, creative competence, model, methodology, stages, preparation, universality.

We believe that the use of methods, forms, and tools used in the process of teaching English to non-philology students contributes to the development of their creative competence, as well as their acquisition of the competencies envisioned in the MBS.

At the research stage, a review of scientific literature and regulatory documents related to the research topic was conducted, and an analysis of the level of development of the problem under study was conducted. During interviews with university and secondary school teachers, the relevance of the research topic was confirmed by practicing teachers and potential employers. They noted that university graduates do not sufficiently understand the role of creative activity in the professional activity of a teacher.

Observing non-philology students has shown that most students possess creative abilities, but they are manifested only in extracurricular activities: participation in various events of the institute and university (competitions, concerts, etc.). During the conversation, most students expressed that they do not see opportunities to engage in creative activities within the framework of the educational process (especially in the study of natural sciences). Taking into account the results of the theoretical analysis of scientific literature, interviews with teachers and students, as well as observations of non-philology students, the subject, goal, object and objectives of the research were determined, the structure and levels of development of their creative competence were determined, and their development in the educational process at the university was considered.

By the 3rd-4th year of university studies, the situation changes somewhat: students' self-assessment of their creative qualities becomes more objective, and the number of students with developed verbal and figurative creativity, as well as variability in thinking, increases significantly. This is related to the individual (episodic) implementation by senior students of the model of English language acquisition and development of creative competence, indicated in the paragraphs, in the educational process: student participation in setting lesson objectives, the use of research and heuristic teaching methods, seminars, presented in the form of a prepared lecture.

During the observation of students in these groups, interviews with teachers of professional disciplines and heads of pedagogical practice, we came to the conclusion that students are not realizing their creative potential in pedagogical (educational) activity. This was also confirmed by a questionnaire, in which students were asked the following questions:

Do you consider yourself a creative person? What types of creative competence do you engage in?

2. How is your creative competence manifested in learning activities?

3. In your opinion, what role does the development of creative competence play in your future professional activity?

4. Do you associate creative activity, future professional activity, and English language activity?

5. In your opinion, does the teacher's creative competence contribute to improving the quality of student learning? Explain your point.

6. Do you see opportunities for developing students' creative competence by integrating the subjects of your specialty with English?

Analysis of student responses showed that almost 63% of respondents do not see a connection between creative competence and professional activity.

At the same time, as indicated in Chapter 1, it is advisable to consider creative competence as an integral part of a teacher's professional competence.

We believe that the implementation of the methodology for developing the creative competence of non-philology students in the process of teaching English, presented in the work, will help resolve this contradiction.

References:

1. Ефремова Н.Ф. Подходы к оцениванию компетенций в высшем образовании: учебное пособие. – М.: Исследовательский центр проблем качества подготовки специалистов, 2010. – С. 106.

2. https://www.testingmom.com/tests/torrance-test/?srsltid=AmBOop-e-dPbMfAAuIeQ0h7oIDLCBV0-qt024_W5bPaqLmwDz9RKHox

3. Бекешева (Егорова) И.С. Специальный комплекс креативно-ориентированных математических заданий, направленных на формирование креативной компетентности будущих бакалавров-учителей: учебное пособие. – Абакан: Издательство Хакасского государственного университета им. Н.Ф.Катанова, 2017. – 48 с.
4. Лобок А. Профессиональная педагогическая экспертиза: как преодолеть миражи // Воспитание. Образование. Педагогика: биб-ка «Первого сентября». – 2008. – № 13. – С. 43.

